

DISTRIBUTED TERRITORIES OF THE TAMARICACEAE FAMILY IN SURKHANDARYA

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Abstract. Representatives of the Tamaricaceae family distributed in the Surkhandarya region, geography, climate, groundwater, distribution of the Tamaricaceae species in the Surkhandarya region, meeting areas, homeland and adaptation of the Tamaricaceae species.

Keywords: tamarix species, habitats, soil structure, number of species, meeting area.

РАСПРЕДЕЛЕННЫЕ ТЕРРИТОРИИ СЕМЕЙСТВА TAMARICACEAE В СУРХАНДАРЬЕ

Аннотация. Представители семейства Tamaricaceae, распространенные в Сурхандарьинской области, география, климат, подземные воды, распространение видов Tamaricaceae в Сурхандарьинской области, ареалы встреч, родина и адаптация видов Tamaricaceae.

Ключевые слова: тамарикс, местообитания, структура почвы, численность, место встречи.

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INTRODUCTION

In the world today, Tamaris are generally adapted to arid climates due to their efficient and deep root system. These species grow in common habitats from flooding to drought, but best grow in sandy or gravelly soils, and are also tolerant of salt water. They are usually used as ornamental flowering shrubs, but are also planted to stabilize sea breezes or sand dunes. Some species are invasive plants in many countries for their ability to colonize and expand rapidly.

Tamarix is found naturally in Western Europe and the Mediterranean to North Africa, northeastern China, Mongolia, India, and Japan. There are 14 species recorded in Europe.

African tamarisk (Tamarix africana), Bovening tamarisk (Tamarix boveana), Canary tamarisk (Tamarix canariensis), Dalmatian tamarisk (Tamarix dalmatica), French tamarisk (Tamarix gallica), Hampe's tamarisk (Tamarix hampeana), small-flowered tamarisk, Smyrna tamarisk (Tamarix smyrnensis) and four-tailed tamarisk (Tamarix tetrandia) are native to the Mediterranean region, mainly France, Spain, Portugal, Italy and Greece and Turkey.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Tamarix ramosissima type, Tamarix laxa, Tamarix hispida, Tamarix gracilis and Tamarix meyeri are native to Eastern Europe, Moldova, Russia and Ukraine.

tamarisk, (genus tamarix), a species of false tamarisk (Myricaria 10 species) 54 species of shrubs and many species of low trees growing in saline deserts, seashores, mountainous areas

and other semi-arid areas (Tamaricaceae family). Introduced from the Mediterranean region to Central Asia and North China, as well as North America.

Today, in Uzbekistan, the area of alfalfa is 250,000 hectares. They grow mainly in the tugai forests of sandy deserts, on low or flat lands, in strongly saline soils. The eruption is often found in old riverbeds or at the bottom of dry lakes. It can be found in saxaul and other desert shrubs covered with salt marshes. In Uzbekistan, there are 16 species of lizards belonging to 3 families. The central group of the family is Yulgun (Tamarix). [1; 210-b.]. There are 75 species of the genus, and 12 species in Uzbekistan. Species such as *T. arceuthoides* (*T. arceuthoides*), Litvinov yulgun (*T. litvinovii*) grow in all regions of the country on the banks of rivers, streams, around lakes in the desert. In addition, soft willow (*T. laxa*), sernam, coarse hairy willow (*T. hispida*) are found in river basins. [2; 206-b.].

RESEARCH RESULTS

Surkhandarya region is located in the south-eastern part of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is bounded on three sides by mountains, bordering the Republic of Tajikistan to the north and northeast, the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan to the south across the Amu Darya, the Republic of Turkmenistan to the southwest, and the Kashkadarya Province to the northwest. The southern irrigated areas of the lower reaches of the Surkhandarya and Sherabad rivers consist of plains. It is surrounded on the north and west by the Boysun and Kohitang mountains, which are a continuation of the Gissar mountain range, and on the east by the Bobotag mountain range.

The total land area of the region is 20.1 thousand sq. Km, 9-10 thousand sq. Km consists of plains, hills and hills, the remaining 10-11 thousand sq. Km are 1500-4500 meters above sea level and above. consists of mountain ranges. [5 .., 6 ..].

Climate. The climate of the Surkhandarya valley is dry subtropical. But as you climb the surrounding mountains, the climate changes. Summers are sunny, hot and dry in the plains of the district, and the temperature drops to the mountains. Winters are short and warm, but colder in the surrounding mountains.

In summer, the flat part of the county gets very hot. In the southern Surkhandarya region, the weather is very dry, almost different from other regions, the average annual relative humidity is 43-54%, in July it decreases to 24-32%, in winter it increases to 62-66%, during the growing season the average is 41-44 % is observed.

DISCUSSION

Groundwater occurs between deposits of different periods. Fresh water flows from a depth of 140-150 m between the Paleogene and Neogene deposits. The temperature of mineral healing water between the Cretaceous deposits at a depth of 1000-2000 m reaches +60 + 70 ° C.

Soils. Light gray soils are distributed in the Surkhandarya natural geographical district up to 500 m above sea level.

Where groundwater is close to the surface, saline gray soils are found. Alluvial-meadow and swampy soils are found on the banks of the Surkhandarya and Sherabad rivers, while sandy and loamy soils are found in the southern part of the sand massifs.

Simple and dark gray soils are distributed in the area of the district from 500 m to 1200 m. [6].

According to the study, representatives of the tamaricaceae family, the community of gardeners of Qizirik district and the community of Qoratepa mahalla of Oltinsoy district in

Surkhan Street in the alluvial sandy desert areas around the roadsides and riverbeds. semi-hydromorphic, can be found in hydromorphized regions (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Kyzylryk district Gardeners' mahalla, Altynsai district Qoratepa mfy Surkhan street

The following types of tamarinds are found in the Surkhandarya region.

Tamarix bungei Boiss. (*Tamariks bungei*) Distributed in the deserts and hills of Surkhandarya region.

Tamarix florida Bge. (*Tamarix Florida*) is found in the desert hills of the region, on the terraces of the Surkhandarya and Amudarya rivers.

Tamarix arceuthoides Bge. (*Tamarix arkeutoides*) grows in the mountainous areas of the region.

Tamarix hohenackori Bge. (*Tamarix hohenakori*) is distributed in the mountainous areas of the region

Tamarix pentandra Pall. (*Tamarix pentandra*) has been identified in the desert zone of the region.

Tamaix elongate Ledeb. (*Tamariks elongate*) Grows in Surkhandarya State Reserve.

Tamarix romosissima Lbd. (*Tamarix romosissima*) Found in the basins of the Topalang River.

CONCLUSION

Tamarix hispida Willd. (*Yulgun, jingil*) Occurs in the territory of Surkhandarya State Reserve, in the basin of the Topalang River and in the villages around Boysun district [3; 84-b.]. In short, due to the geographical structure of the Surkhandarya region, tamarind species grow mainly in the tugai forests of sandy deserts, low or flat lands, in strongly saline soils. The eruption is often found in old riverbeds or at the bottom of dry lakes.

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